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*ENTREPRENEURIAL EDUCATION IN THE UNIVERSITY ENVIRONMENT:
NATIONAL SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION (2000 TO 2021)*¹

**EDUCAÇÃO EMPREENDEDORA NO AMBIENTE UNIVERSITÁRIO:
PRODUÇÃO CIENTÍFICA NACIONAL (2000 A 2021)**

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ABSTRACT

The mutations of modernity have imposed new configurations on society – social, cultural, political, economic, technological. Issues such as economic downturn, social movements that seek space in the arc of power, diffuse political articulations, cultural imbroglis, debates about gender, concerns about the environment, etc. have moved scholars to build an agenda that effectively responds to the demands of society, especially socially vulnerable ones. Taking this reality as an economic foundation, the study aims to analyze the characteristics of national scientific production related to entrepreneurial education in universities, represented by articles published in national journals. This purpose is inferred from the relevance of the topic in the current socioeconomic scenario. It is concluded that there was an evolution in the number of publications on the topic, especially between the years 2016 to 2021, indicating the expansion of debates, cases and practices regarding the insertion of Entrepreneurial Education in the academic environment, which is why it is suggested an agenda for future research in the field, aiming to stimulate new perspectives that are capable of incorporating youth into the field of entrepreneurship, as a legitimate alternative for personal and professional fulfillment.

Keywords: entrepreneurial education, entrepreneurship teaching, college education, bibliometrics, national scientific production.

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RESUMO

As mutações da modernidade têm imposto, à sociedade, novas configurações – sociais, culturais, políticas, econômicas, tecnológicas. Questões como retração econômica, movimentos sociais que buscam espaços no arco de poder, difusas articulações políticas, imbrólios culturais, debates sobre gênero, preocupações com o meio ambiente, etc. têm movimentado os estudiosos na construção de uma agenda que responda eficazmente às demandas da sociedade, especialmente as socialmente vulneráveis. Tomando esta realidade como fundamento econômico, o estudo objetiva analisar as características da produção científica nacional relacionada à educação empreendedora nas universidades, representada pelos artigos publicados em periódicos nacionais. Tal propósito infere-se na relevância do tema no cenário socioeconômico atual. Conclui-se que houve uma evolução no número de publicações sobre o tema, especialmente entre os anos de 2016 a 2021, indicando a ampliação dos debates, *cases* e práticas no que concerne à inserção da Educação Empreendedora na ambiência acadêmica, razão pela qual se sugere uma agenda para futuras pesquisas no campo, visando estimular novas perspectivas que sejam capazes de incorporar a juventude para o campo do empreendedorismo, como uma alternativa legítima de realização pessoal e profissional.

Palavras-Chave: educação empreendedora, ensino de empreendedorismo, educação superior, bibliometria, produção científica nacional.

INTRODUCTION

It seems there is a consensus in the academic environment, in the economic field, and in society that entrepreneurship is a consolidated, promising, and necessary topic, especially in developing countries that thus need to stimulate entrepreneurial initiative as a way to reduce social inequalities, as well as to foster new business perspectives in order to address economic imbalances. When related to practice, it is proven that entrepreneurship constitutes decisions involving public policies to promote initiatives aimed not only at economic development (BOAS; NASCIMENTO, 2020) but, above all, intended to solve issues with social reach.

Thus, it is understandable that, being a relevant issue in the socioeconomic context of a given region, measures are adopted to encourage people to become entrepreneurs, and in this respect, it becomes necessary to give due importance to entrepreneurship education, both in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and in high schools (COELHO, 2020) and elementary schools (FLORIS; DETTORI; REGINATO, 2023), considering that precisely in youth, awakening to the entrepreneurial universe has proven promising, which is why it becomes urgent, with the same vigor, to incorporate and approach this theme in Basic Education - elementary and high school. Although not empirically proven yet, entrepreneurial attitudes that can encourage entrepreneurship as a career option can be highly effective even before high school (KOURILSKY; WALSTAD, 1998).

The dynamics related to entrepreneurial education in higher education have become increasingly prominent and the subject of systematic studies, both in the Brazilian environment (GARCIA et al. 2012; SCHAEFER et al. 2017; LOPES et al. 2021; SILVA et al., 2022; LIMA; TEIXEIRA; ALMEIDA, 2023) and in other countries (DUVAL-COUEIL; REED; HAGHIGHI, 2012; MEI; LEE; XIANG, 2020; VILLARREAL-ÁLVAREZ; ROQUE-HERNÁNDEZ, 2022). In reality, it is possible to verify that entrepreneurial education has promoted positive effects in fostering the entrepreneurial spirit of university students, with emphasis on active pedagogies that have forged the intention and desire to undertake, as evidenced by various studies (RIDEOUT; GRAY, 2013; GUERRERO et al., 2016; TOMY; PARDEDE, 2020; NDOFIREPI, 2020; GREGORIO-MARTINEZ; BADENES-RIBERA; OLIVER, 2021). As Udimal et al. (2020, p. 1) warn, in studies involving BRICS countries, “population growth has a positive effect on all categories of entrepreneurship while unemployment contributes negatively to all categories of entrepreneurship.” From this perspective, it is possible to affirm that entrepreneurship becomes a viable alternative for mitigating unemployment

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levels, and in this particular case, entrepreneurial education constitutes a tool that can help reverse the unfavorable scenario.

Thus, the present study aims to understand how the phenomenon occurs, its characteristics, how it is possible to measure and encourage students' entrepreneurial intention, what reflections in terms of value and effective results entrepreneurial education can provide society, which motivational aspects are present in the teaching-learning process, which techniques can be employed to make pedagogical action more effective and innovative, and to what extent humanistic methods have been developed in academia to advance actions aimed at strengthening the segment and, consequently, reducing social inequalities in the country, given the close relationship between the entrepreneurial approach and connections with social, economic, cultural, and environmental factors. Indeed, understanding what researchers in the field of entrepreneurial education have studied, how research has evolved, and which aspects have surrounded the field is the purpose of this study. For this, prospecting articles available in the Sucupira/CAPES database from 2000 to 2021 (22 years) becomes relevant so that new perceptions about the subject can be promoted.

Having outlined the study design, it is timely to establish the following research problem: What studies were developed and published in national journals from 2000 to 2021 addressing the theme of entrepreneurial education? Based on this proposal, the objective of the study is established, which is to analyze the characteristics of national scientific production in the field of entrepreneurial education from 2000 to 2021, represented by scientific articles published in QUALIS A1, A2, B1, and B2 journals (journal classification for the 2013-2016 quadrennium), considering that at the start of the research the new quadrennium (2017-2020) had not yet been published. Given this context, dissecting the production of scientific knowledge in the field of entrepreneurial education has become an unavoidable initiative, since through it it is possible to

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understand, even amidst the significant volume of information and the numerous transformations that the socioeconomic universe presents today, how a particular field of knowledge has been developing. As Villanova and Silva (2018, p. 11) state,

The need to evaluate the production of knowledge, more specifically institutionalized knowledge, is of utmost importance for society's development. There are several ways to achieve such evaluation; one viable and widely used way is to have bibliographic production as an object of study since it provides important clues that allow for outlining an overview of the directions of science.

That said, it is understood that the study can contribute to the dissemination of knowledge about entrepreneurial education in the country, insofar as it intends to reveal the studies that were developed over a 22-year span, a period of significant social, cultural, economic, and political transformations in Brazil, representing an important space-time to unveil the evolution of studies in the field.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

Scenarios of entrepreneurial education (EE) in universities

Entrepreneurial education has become part of the basic training for a growing number of students, not only those studying business, in an attempt to ensure they are ready for the labor market and the new knowledge society (WILLIAMS, 2019). Entrepreneurial stories are a source of learning about the subject and inspire students to become entrepreneurial agents. Thus, their experiences can influence a person's desire to pursue a career aligned with their learning experiences (PETERMAN; KENNEDY, 2003).

Although universities are implementing broad and diverse approaches to promote and support entrepreneurship, not all entrepreneurship programs facilitate the initiative as a career option for their students (SARDESHMUKH;

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SMITH-NELSON, 2011). Lack of awareness and low attractiveness may be reasons why many students do not choose entrepreneurship as a career, implying the need to develop methodologies capable of bridging potential gaps in student training. Even if undergraduates have developed awareness on the topic, many lack a support network to execute their business idea (JONES et al., 2015).

University education is a key environmental force that enables and provides a way for students to acquire the technical and business skills necessary to nurture their self-efficacy enough to initiate actions for a new venture (ALVAREZ; DENOBLE; JUNG 2006). The university is fundamental for developing the motivation levels and capacities of undergraduates to engage effectively in entrepreneurial activity (PICKERNELL et al., 2011). Broadly speaking, academic entrepreneurship involves all activities and techniques aimed at initiating new businesses, where academic involvement thus becomes essential for promoting such intention (SHAH; PAHNKE, 2014; SIEGEL; WRIGHT, 2015).

Increased competition stimulating innovation and entrepreneurship was active during the wave of globalization. Under unprecedented uncertainty, emerging technology development, and social change, entrepreneurship education plays a critical role in preparing citizens to face the impact of globalization and dramatic educational and social transformation, especially when the locus is China, a developing country (WANG; LEE; TRAPPEY, 2017; LEE; CHEN; TRAPPEY, 2019).

Lackéus (2015) draws attention to the pedagogical potential of entrepreneurial education, specifically its ability to motivate and engage students, as well as its potential to stimulate deep learning. The development of entrepreneurial competencies can also be understood as benefiting the individual by providing a 'life skill' (COSTELLO; NECK; DZIOBEK, 2012; SAGAR, 2015). Pedagogical approaches that include a supportive learning environment make

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entrepreneurship education essential to increasing entrepreneurial intention, as it has been observed that entrepreneurship education can positively influence students to become productive in this field (MAHENDRA; DJATMIKA; HERMAWAN, 2017).

Over the years, several countries have expressed concern in promoting entrepreneurship studies and activities as a way to stimulate growth, economic development, and job creation (GARCÍA-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2017). Fatoki and Oni (2014) suggested that universities need to take center stage in offering quality entrepreneurial education that can motivate individuals to develop a purpose to engage in entrepreneurial activities, and that entrepreneurial education with beginner students can increase entrepreneurial intention and the desire to own a business.

Researchers have focused on digital academic entrepreneurship, which is academic entrepreneurship using digital technologies. Broadly, academic entrepreneurship involves all entrepreneurial activities in which a university can implement focused actions. Dogan (2016) argues that the availability of successful entrepreneurs and the increase in the number of entrepreneurs in a society depend on entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial aspiration. The use of digital technologies not only supports entrepreneurship but also helps manage uncertainties in entrepreneurship (RIPPA; SECUNDO, 2019; TOMY; PARDEDE, 2018).

This system provides various resources, opportunities, skills, and social networks, which can contribute to strengthening entrepreneurial self-efficacy. This effort requires the involvement of university stakeholders, and the use of digital technologies can significantly reduce communication and coordination costs (RIPPA; SECUNDO, 2019). According to Richardson and Hynes (2008), it is important to provide support to accommodate sector-specific needs, such as

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those required by the IT industry, to ensure students are prepared to contribute with their different capabilities to the economic and strategic needs of a country.

Function of entrepreneurial eEducation (EE) in higher education

Entrepreneurial education goes far beyond knowing what it means to be an entrepreneur, as it enables and provides opportunities for daily experiences in dealing with adversity, showing ways to empower and enable the individual, striving to bring beneficial and satisfying experiences. Although this reality is gradually changing, Hofer et al. (2013) still affirm that the rate of undergraduate students (in general) with awareness to undertake is low, even though the study was conducted ten years ago. However, studies by Wan and Lv (2021) show considerable progress in fostering the entrepreneurial spirit in higher education, a space where the subject can be cultivated and learned.

According to Ibitomi and Olamide (2020), individuals have talents that, when properly developed and leveraging all knowledge and skills provided through education, can stimulate significant development that adds benefits to society. Similarly, Garcia-Rodriguez et al. (2017) noted a growing number of countries that have begun to study entrepreneurship more thoroughly, justified by the fact that the subject stimulates job creation and economic development. In their study, Mefi and Asoba (2022) pointed to a known theory of goal-setting and mindset, which brings a concept of the need to set entrepreneurial goals (focus and deadline) to achieve desired outcomes, all based on proposed objectives.

Following this line of thought, entrepreneurship in higher education can also be characterized as a link for outlining such goals from the start of each idea, whether developed in the classroom or applied daily. According to Shapero (1975), some dimensions can be observed that engage students in considering whether or not to become entrepreneurs: perceived desirability; perceived feasibility; and the propensity to act. All these factors help the student develop an

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outlook and plan steps to know if entrepreneurship is truly their desire and viable for their immersion in the entrepreneurial world.

Taneja and Bhatia (2022), in a study applied in India, point out that studying entrepreneurship has gained political attention. Much of this focus emphasizes individual skills that may arise, making the subject an integral part of curricula in several universities. Besides undergraduate programs, India also offers postgraduate entrepreneurship courses lasting 1 to 2 years, believing that this topic enables individual growth and development, contributing to the reduction of social fissures.

According to Novanda (2022), in a study conducted in Indonesia, entrepreneurship has been demanded by students themselves, who see the subject or course as a way to motivate thinking differently, acting, and deciding creatively, with many career path possibilities in the labor market. It is important to note that students request this topic based on good experiences and recurring positive accounts, implying that such reality allows their minds to be open to new opportunities. Indonesia is among the leading countries in entrepreneurship research, although studies (HANDAYATI et al., 2020) indicate a low number of entrepreneurs, evidenced by the high unemployment rate. Mawardi and Sahputri (2022) developed a study focused on Indonesia, which found a higher willingness and availability to undertake among students who already have some guidance on the topic, usually obtained within the family context.

Luco and Granados (2014) relate the desire to undertake with psychosocial factors indicating the student's willingness to link positive experiences to this subject, associating it with pleasant or unpleasant experiences personally. Similarly, Fischer et al. (2022) connected successful startups with innovative intentions and good entrepreneurial pedagogical didactics, aiming to direct competencies through individuals' specific knowledge.

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Responsibility of higher education institutions (HEIs) in developing the entrepreneurial spirit

Since the 2000s, entrepreneurship education has been offered from compulsory education to universities in both developed and developing countries (CRAMMOND, 2020). It is suggested, therefore, that entrepreneurship education be integrated into academic curricula at all levels, from elementary school to university (STEVENSON; LUNDSTROM, 2001). As Raposo, Paço, and Ferreira (2008) affirm, integrating entrepreneurship into academic curricula can contribute to creating a conducive environment for learning and creativity, thus increasing awareness and knowledge in specific business areas. HEIs then become instrumental in fostering the entrepreneurial spirit. According to Fayolle, Gailly, and Clerc (2006), the pedagogical workload teaching ways to undertake, allowing imagination to flow, and using appropriate didactics to develop skills along with attitudes, motivates individuals to develop a critical and keen sense about the theme, inspiring them to immerse themselves in thought-action.

Indeed, entrepreneurship education should include behavioral simulations and areas such as negotiation, leadership, creative thinking, technological innovation, and new product development, as well as discovering and exploring new business opportunities, long-term business planning, among other skills and characteristics (MCMULLAN; LONGO; GRAHAM, 1986; VESPER; MCMULLAN; RONSTADT, 1988). Worldwide, entrepreneurs are found in all professions - education, medicine, law, architecture, engineering, social work, distribution, and government - proving that these professions, while having their peculiarities, embrace an innovative business environment (BARON, 1998). The strategic importance of entrepreneurship in economic development has triggered an explosion of entrepreneurship education programs worldwide (ROXAS; CAYOCA-PANIZALES, 2009). The concept of entrepreneurship education has also become an important economic and social phenomenon, as

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well as a popular research topic that has become a promising area in academia and teaching (LEKOKO; RANKHUMISE; RAS, 2012).

Entrepreneurship education should focus on real-world experience, action, and reflective processes, engaging students in authentic learning, promoting a stimulating learning process, cultivating their entrepreneurial competencies, and transforming inclinations into behaviors (KASSEAN et al. 2015). The results show a growing need for educational programs in entrepreneurship as academic training significantly impacts the acquisition of skills, attitudes, and aspirations, which can be useful in improving and boosting the development of potential entrepreneurs (RAPOSO; PAÇO; FERREIRA, 2008). It is vital to identify personality traits and skills reflected in successful entrepreneurs so that entrepreneurship education and training curricula can be effectively designed according to country needs (GUROL; ATSAN, 2006).

Therefore, "by taking on the task of training competent individuals with entrepreneurial orientation, universities need to generate social mechanisms that support and facilitate the birth and growth of businesses" (PETRIDOU; SARRI; KYRGIDOU, 2009, p. 290). Abdullah and Septiany (2019) understand that entrepreneurial knowledge can be found through learning entrepreneurial theories obtained through various media, including experiences of other entrepreneurs. According to Lynskey (2005), considering the role of higher education in societies and regional and national economic development, universities should be seen as "knowledge engines," focusing again on the not only educational but also social role HEIs have in the global entrepreneurial context. Thus, students' relationship with entrepreneurship depends on entrepreneurial theories they know and which are developed by the faculty. Abdullah and Septiany (2019) assert that these theories need to be presented through capable institutions to maximize the dissemination and absorption of information about entrepreneurship.

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Therefore, universities play a crucial role collaborating with industry and government to expand research and knowledge and jointly obtain funding with industry for further development, assisting in the formation of new companies in incubator facilities, providing consulting, and helping promote entrepreneurship (ETZKOWITZ; ZHOU, 2008). The positive influence of entrepreneurship education in universities contributes to forming a useful and inspiring career path for students (GALLOWAY; BROWN, 2002), implying the adoption of strategies aimed at strengthening this segment in the academic environment.

METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES

The success of any scientific research depends on the methodology implemented. Properly defining the methodology ensures that the investigation process will reach a good outcome, founded on its reliability and validity (both internal and external), as highlighted by Pereira (2021). In this sense, to support the ongoing research proposal, bibliometrics will be adopted as the research technique. This study is descriptive-exploratory with a quantitative approach. Bibliometrics is a technique that emerged in the early 20th century as a response to the need for studies, surveys, and evaluations of scientific production and communication within a particular human knowledge field. According to Mugnaini (2013, p. 39), “the volume of scientific and technological information stimulated the development of complex information retrieval techniques, raising another issue concerning the difficulty of appropriating published knowledge,” hence the relevance of bibliometric techniques. Marcelo and Hayashi (2013, p. 143) define bibliometric studies as having “the main characteristic of creating indices of scientific knowledge production. The use of bibliometric analysis in scientific research is based on investigating knowledge behavior and literature as part of communication processes.”

Bibliometrics thus provides researchers a holistic view of their study areas, leading to scientific advances by facilitating the visualization of gaps related to a specific theme through categorizing previously conducted studies. For this study, the SUCUPIRA platform was chosen, using journal classification for the 2013-2016 quadrennium, in the evaluation area of Public Administration and Business, Accounting Sciences, and Tourism, along with ISSN (International Standard Serial Number) to identify the origin/territorial base of mapped journals, distinguishing national journals from international ones. Search filters included the expressions: “educação empreendedora,” “entrepreneurial education,” “empreendedorismo universitário,” “university entrepreneurship,” “empreendedorismo no ensino superior,” and “entrepreneurship in higher education,” given that some journals, even those nationally based, predominantly publish articles in English.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

Searches conducted between November 2022 and February 2023 identified the number of publications involving Entrepreneurial Education in national journals, based on the keyword filter. Chart 1 presents the systematization of these publications, using the SUCUPIRA Platform as a reference.

Chart 1 – Number of journals obtained in Plataforma Sucupira

Stratum	National	International	Actual Quantity (*)	Official Quantity
A1	1	322	323	323
A2	67	383	450	473
B1	193	195	388	454
B2	213	141	354	427
TOTAL	474	1.041	1.515	1.677

Source: Research data, 2022-2023.

(*) Number of journals effectively accessed on the Sucupira Platform

(**) Number of journals indicated on the Sucupira Platform

In Table 1, it is possible to see that during the access to the Sucupira Platform, 1,677 journals were obtained. However, as the presentation pages of

the journals were analyzed, the actual quantity reached was 1,515 journals, which serves as the basis for the study. Chart 2 shows that, within the studied time frame, there were no publications on the subject in a single national journal classified as QUALIS A1. In the same table, it is observed that 71 articles addressing the investigated theme were published, considering the six filters used in the query.

Chart 2 – Summary of searches in journals by filter (6 keywords)

Total journals by stratum		Total articles published		Filters used in the query	
A2	67	A2	21	Educação Empreendedora.....	35
B1	193	B1	19	Entrepreneurial Education.....	14
B2	213	B2	31	Empreendedorismo Universitário.....	8
				Empreendedorismo no Ensino Superior.....	7
				University Entrepreneurship.....	6
				Entrepreneurship in Higher Education.....	1
Total journals		Total articles			
473		71			

Source: Research data, 2022-2023.

Chart 3 lists the journals that published the 71 articles during the period from 2000 to 2021, highlighting the journals *Pensamento Contemporâneo em Administração* (UFF) and *Cadernos EBAPE* (FGV), which together accounted for 24% of all articles published during this period.

Chart 3 – Journals that published studies involving the theme (2000 a 2021)

Journals	Number of publications in the period	QUALIS
Revista Pensamento Contemporâneo em Administração – RPCA	9	B2
Caderno EBAPE (Escola Brasileira de Administração Pública e de Empresas)	8	A2
Administração: Ensino e Pesquisa (RAEP)	4	B1
Revista de Administração da UFSM	4	B1
Revista de Ciências da Administração	4	B2
Open Journal of Social Sciences	3	B2
Brazilian Administration Review (BAR)	3	A2
Revista Pretexto	3	B1
Revista Eletrônica de Ciência Administrativa (RECADM)	3	B1
Desenvolvimento em Questão	3	B2
Revista de Administração de Empresas (RAE)	2	A2
Brazilian Business Review (BBR)	2	A2
Independent Journal of Management & Production	2	B1

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Chart 3 – Journals that published studies involving the theme (2000 a 2021) (continuation)

Journals	Number of publications in the period	QUALIS
Revista Eletrônica de Administração (READ)	2	B1
Revista Gestão Organizacional (ONLINE) (RGO)	2	B2
Revista Economia e Gestão	2	B2
Revista de Administração da UNIMEP	2	B2
Revista de Administração FACES Journal	2	B2
Anais da Academia Brasileira de Ciências (AABC)	1	A2
Revista Brasileira de Gestão de Negócios (RBGN)	1	A2
Educação e Sociedade	1	A2
Revista Latino-Americana de Enfermagem	1	A2
Revista Brasileira de Enfermagem	1	B1
Revista da Escola de Enfermagem da USP	1	B1
Revista de Escola de Enfermagem da UFSM	1	B1
Revista da Rede de Enfermagem do Nordeste	1	B2
Revista Gestão Universitária na América Latina	1	B2
Ensino e Pesquisa em Administração – RAEP	1	B2
Revista de Enfermagem UERJ	1	B2
Total de Publicações	71	

Source: Research data, 2022-2023.

Chart 4 indicates the most prolific authors who published on entrepreneurial education (EE). The criterion adopted was at least two publications within the study's time frame, and Graph 1 presents a timeline indicating the evolution of studies published during the historical period covered by the research.

Chart 4 - Most productive authors on the topic (period from 2000 to 2021)

Author	Published articles			Total production by author	Year of publication
	A2	B1	B2		
Sílvia Maria Dias Pedro Rebouças	2		1	3	2015, 2018, 2020
José Luís Guedes dos Santos	1	1	1	3	2017, 2020, 2021
Italo Fernando Minello		2	1	3	2016, 2017, 2019
Luís Eduardo Brandão Paiva	2			2	2018, 2020
Raimundo Eduardo Silveira Fontenele	2			2	2018, 2020
Edson Sadao Iizuka	1	1		2	2014, 2018
Cristiane Krüger		1	1	2	2017, 2019
Fernanda Hannah da Silva Copelli		1	1	2	2017, 2020
Gerson Antonio Melatti		1	1	2	2013, 2011
Gracyanne Freire de Araújo		1	1	2	2018, 2020
Rafaela Escobar Bürger		1	1	2	2017, 2019
Saulo Fabiano Amâncio Vieira		1	1	2	2011, 2013
Vânia Maria Jorge Nassif		1	1	2	2012, 2020
Cristina Dai Prá Martens			2	2	2019, 2020
Jairo de Carvalho Guimarães			2	2	2016, 2020

Source: Research data, 2022-2023.

Graph 1 – Overview of publications by year × filters (in both languages) × quantity

Source: Research data, 2022-2023.

Chart 5 systematizes the studies conducted in the 10 journals with the most publications, considering the research's time frame.

Chart 5 – Ranking of the 10 journals with the most publications and their respective studies, presented in order of quantity

Qualis	JOURNAL TITLE	YEAR	ARTICLE TITLE	AUTHORS	PARTICIPANTS, COURSE OF THE RESEARCH, HEI, CITY AND STATE
A2	Cadernos EBAPE	2014	Sucesso, mídia de negócios e a cultura do management no Brasil.	Cristiana Trindade Ituassu; Maria José Tonelli	Not Identified
		2016	Eu, Alex, da etnia Guarani: o testemunho de um estudante indígena de administração e seu duplo pertencimento	Marcio Pascoal Cassandre; Wagner Roberto do Amaral; Alexandro da Silva	Indigenous students present in universities, State University of Maringá; State University of Londrina.
		2017	Preditores individuais e contextuais da intenção empreendedora entre universitários: revisão de literatura	Marcio da Silva Moreira Ferreira; Elisabeth Loiola; Sônia Maria Guedes Gondim	University students, Federal University of Bahia / School of Administration, Salvador – BA.

Continues

Chart 5 – Ranking of the 10 journals with the most publications and their respective studies, presented in order of quantity (continuation)

Qualis	JOURNAL TITLE	YEAR	ARTICLE TITLE	AUTHORS	PARTICIPANTS, COURSE OF THE RESEARCH, HEI, CITY AND STATE
A2	Cadernos EBAPE	2018	Pesquisa de empreendedorismo (2000-2014) nas seis principais revistas brasileiras de administração: lacunas e direcionamento.	Antonio Benedito de Oliveira Junior; Cristiane Chaves Gattaz; Roberto Carlos Bernardes; Edson Sadao Iizuka	Bibliometric study
			Influência da sustentabilidade e da inovação na intenção empreendedora de universitários brasileiros e portugueses	Luis Eduardo Brandão Paiva; Tereza Cristina Batista de Lima; Sílvia Maria Dias Pedro Rebouças; Eugênia Maria Dores Maia Ferreira; Raimundo Eduardo Silveira Fontenele	Undergraduate students from the Federal University of Ceará (Brazil) and the University of Algarve (Portugal). Federal University of Ceará; University of Algarve.
		2020	Pesquisa em empreendedorismo: a produção científica francófona em perspectivas	Alex Fernando Borges; Alessandro Gomes Enoque	Students of Administration, Accounting Sciences, and Production Engineering. Ituiutaba – MG, Federal University of Uberlândia (UFU).
			Entre o discurso empreendedor e a consciência política: estudo exploratório do movimento Empresa Júnior em uma universidade pública no sudeste do Brasil	Márcia Prezotti Palassi; Raiane Gonçalves de Oliveira Martinelli; Ana Paula Paes de Paula	Junior entrepreneurs at one campus of a federal public university in southeastern Brazil. Federal University of Espírito Santo (UFES); Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG).

Continues

Chart 5 – Ranking of the 10 journals with the most publications and their respective studies, presented in order of quantity (continuation)

Qualis	JOURNAL TITLE	YEAR	ARTICLE TITLE	AUTHORS	PARTICIPANTS, COURSE OF THE RESEARCH, HEI, CITY AND STATE
A2	Cadernos EBAPE	2020	A influência das crenças religiosas na intenção empreendedora: uma análise sob perspectiva da teoria do comportamento planejado	Evangelina da Silva Sousa; Luís Eduardo Brandão Paiva; Alexandre Rodrigues Santos; Sílvia Maria Dias Pedro Rebouças; Raimundo; Eduardo Silveira Fontenele	University students from undergraduate programs in the Administration course at two universities in the Northeast region, one located in Ceará and the other in Piauí, both offering subjects related to entrepreneurship. Federal University of Ceará (UFC); Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB).
A2	Brazilian Administration Review – BAR	2020	University ecosystems and the commitment of faculty members to support entrepreneurial activity.	Gustavo Moraes; Bruno Fischer; Matheus Campos; Paola Scheffer	Faculty members from over 70 higher education institutions across all regions of Brazil.
		2021	Entrepreneurship education and its influence on higher education students	Lisete Mónico; Carla Carvalho; Samuel Nejoti; Marco Arraya; Pedro Parreira	Students were selected from the University of Coimbra, Portugal, as well as from other Portuguese higher education institutions.
			Evaluating the effect of entrepreneurial programs elements on students	Elda Barron; Elizabeth Ruiz	University students from 3 universities.
B1	Revista Eletrônica de Ciência Administrativa (RECADM)	2003	Políticas e incentivos ao empreendedorismo em instituições de ensino superior (IES) – Uma nova abordagem para a gestão educacional	Günther Lothar Pertschy; Raul Otto Laux	Not identified

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Chart 5 – Ranking of the 10 journals with the most publications and their respective studies, presented in order of quantity (continuation)

Qualis	JOURNAL TITLE	YEAR	ARTICLE TITLE	AUTHORS	PARTICIPANTS, COURSE OF THE RESEARCH, HEI, CITY AND STATE
B1	Revista de Ciências da Administração	2006	Empreendedorismo e educação empreendedora: Confrontação entre a teoria e prática	João Benjamim Cruz Júnior; Pedro da Costa Araújo; Sérgio Machado Wolf; Tatiana V. A. Ribeiro	87 micro or small entrepreneurs. Santa Catarina, Rio Grande do Sul, São Paulo, and Mato Grosso do Sul, UFSC.
		2007	A contribuição do curso de administração da Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina para o desenvolvimento de competências empreendedoras	Andressa Sasaki Vasques Pacheco; Luís Moretto Neto	Students of the Administration course. Federal University of Santa Catarina, Santa Catarina.
		2009	Empreendedorismo e Jovens Empreendedores	Dario de Oliveira Lima-Filho; Renato Luiz Sproesser; Eber Luis Capistrano Martins	16 young middle-class entrepreneurs, graduates of Entrepreneurship courses. Cuiabá-MT.
	Administração: Ensino e Pesquisa – RAEP	2011	Ensino de empreendedorismo nos cursos presenciais de Graduação em administração em Fortaleza: um estudo dos conteúdos e instrumentos pedagógicos	Estevão Lima de Carvalho Rocha; Gino Augusto Bacchi; Diego de Souza Guerra; Estélio Menezes Rôla Júnior; Daniel Rodriguez de Carvalho Pinheiro	Undergraduate Administration courses in the city of Fortaleza, CE.
	Revista de Administração da UFSM	2011	O ensino de empreendedorismo nos cursos de Graduação em Administração: um estudo comparativo entre as universidades estaduais de Londrina e Maringá	Saulo Fabiano Amâncio Vieira; Gerson Antonio Melatti; Paula Regina Ribeiro	Course coordinators of the aforementioned institutions, State Universities of Londrina and Maringá, PR

continues

Chart 5 – Ranking of the 10 journals with the most publications and their respective studies, presented in order of quantity (continuation)

Qualis	JOURNAL TITLE	YEAR	ARTICLE TITLE	AUTHORS	PARTICIPANTS, COURSE OF THE RESEARCH, HEI, CITY AND STATE
B1	Administração: Ensino e Pesquisa – RAEP	2012	A universidade desenvolve competências empreendedoras? Um mapeamento das práticas de ensino numa universidade brasileira	Vânia Maria Jorge Nassif; Derly Jardim do Amaral; Rodrigo Augusto Prando	The research included directors, course coordinators, and professors indicated by the directors, from two HEIs (not identified in the article) in São Paulo.
	Revista Eletrônica de Ciência Administrativa (RECADM)	2013	Correlação entre elementos do capital social e orientação empreendedora: um estudo exploratório	Rosana da Rosa Portella Tondolo; Vilmar Antonio Gonçalves Tondolo; Claudia Cristina Bitencourt	Students from the Administration and Accounting Sciences courses at a Higher Education Institution (HEI) in southern Brazil.
	Administração: Ensino e Pesquisa – RAEP	2014	Análise do potencial e perfil empreendedor do estudante de administração e o ambiente universitário: Reflexões para instituições de ensino	Edson Sadao Iizuka; Gustavo Hermínio Salati Marcondes de Moraes	Administration student from a private educational institution and the students' perspective on the university environment. Federal University of Santa Catarina.
	Revista de Administração da UFSM	2017	Características comportamentais empreendedoras: um estudo com acadêmicos de administração de uma universidade brasileira	Italo Fernando Minello; Rafaela Escobar Bürger; Cristiane Krüger	Undergraduate Administration students, UFSM (Palmeira das Missões Campus and Santa Maria Campus).
	Revista Eletrônica de Ciência Administrativa (RECADM)	2019	Autodeterminação e Empreendedorismo com Suporte em Motivações: análise empírica com universitários do curso de administração	Fabiana Pinto de Almeida Bizarria; Flávia Lorene Sampaio Barbosa; Antônia Márcia Rodrigues Sousa	Administration university students from 7 Higher Education Institutions located in three cities in the Northeast.

continues

Chart 5 – Ranking of the 10 journals with the most publications and their respective studies, presented in order of quantity (continuation)

Qualis	JOURNAL TITLE	YEAR	ARTICLE TITLE	AUTHORS	PARTICIPANTS, COURSE OF THE RESEARCH, HEI, CITY AND STATE
B1	Revista de Ciências da Administração	2019	<i>Mindset</i> , dificuldades em se empreender e o potencial empreendedor: uma abordagem confirmatória com estudantes graduandos em administração.	Frederico Leocádio Ferreira; Pâmella Otone Bandeira; Carlos Alberto Gonçalves	Administration students, Belo Horizonte (MG).
	Administração: Ensino e Pesquisa – RAEP	2020	Experiência Emocional na Educação Empreendedora: Emoção como Dinâmica de Aprendizagem	Gracyanne Freire de Araujo; Eduardo Paes Barreto Davel	Between 30 and 40 students in the undergraduate Administration course, Federal University of Sergipe, Itabaiana (SE).
	Revista de Administração da UFSM	2020	Modeling entrepreneurial intent as a predictor of frugal innovation in university students	Luis Felipe Dias Lopes; Sirlene Aparecida Takeda Bresciani; Denise Adriana Johann; Gilnei Luiz de Moura; Damiana Machado de Almeida; Clarissa Stefani Teixeira	Undergraduate students enrolled in Administration, Accounting Sciences, Economics, Civil Engineering, and Electrical Engineering courses, State University of Mato Grosso – UNEMAT, Mato Grosso.
			Influência da educação empreendedora no desenvolvimento da autoeficácia e das competências empreendedoras	Carolina Maria Furtado Matos; Suzete Antonieta Lizote; Sayonara de Fátima Teston; Patrick Zawadzki; Maria Cristina Almeida Gama Guerra	Undergraduate students from Health-related courses, Community University of Southern Brazil.

continues

Chart 5 – Ranking of the 10 journals with the most publications and their respective studies, presented in order of quantity (continuation)

Qualis	JOURNAL TITLE	YEAR	ARTICLE TITLE	AUTHORS	PARTICIPANTS, COURSE OF THE RESEARCH, HEI, CITY AND STATE
B2	Revista Pretexto	2009	Projeto arquimedes: Empreendedorismo nas instituições de ensino superior	Frederico Alberto Gurgel e Silva, Rosa Cristina Lima Ribeiro, Francisco Roberto Pinto, Leonel Gois Lima Oliveira	Students from Higher Education Institutions in Fortaleza, undergraduates from 7 HEIs in Fortaleza, CE.
	Revista Pensamento Contemporâneo em Administração	2013	Adaptação, validação e discussões da aplicação de uma escala de medida do potencial empreendedor em universitários	Ana Cristina Ferreira; Valderi de Castro Alcântara; Fernanda. Machado Freitas	Students from a public Higher Education Institution (HEI).
		2014	Contribuição da pedagogia freireana na formação de administradores empreendedores	Rosivaldo de Lima Lucena; Wanusa Campos Centurión; José de Arimatéia Dias Valadão	Not Identified.
			Determinantes para a formação da cultura empreendedora: a experiência do projeto desafio SEBRAE.	Maurício Mendes Boavista de Castro; Sérgio Aquino de Souza; João Carlos Hipólito B. Nascimento; Leonardo Victor de Sá Pinheiro; Juliana Reis Bernardes	University student from Piauí who participated in the SEBRAE business challenge game. SEBRAE-PI.
			A formação do administrador na perspectiva das competências individuais requeridas	Donizeti Leandro de Souza; Donizeti Leandro de Souza; Robert Delano de Souza Corrêa; André Luiz Zambalde	Graduating students from Bachelor's programs in Administration at three private HEIs located in the Triângulo Mineiro/Alto Paranaíba region and southern Minas Gerais.

continues

Chart 5 – Ranking of the 10 journals with the most publications and their respective studies, presented in order of quantity (continuation)

Qualis	JOURNAL TITLE	YEAR	ARTICLE TITLE	AUTHORS	PARTICIPANTS, COURSE OF THE RESEARCH, HEI, CITY AND STATE
B2	Open Journal of Social Sciences	2014	Entrepreneurial Skill Needs of Secretarial Education Graduates of Colleges of Education for Self Sustainability in Enugu State, Nigeria	E. A. C. Etonyeaku; J. A. Kanu; H. A. Ezeji; J. N. Chukwuma	Graduates in Secretarial Studies from the Faculty of Education, Enugu State, Nigeria.
		2015	Conhecimento Empreendedor e a Influência da Educação Empreendedora nas Habilidades Empreendedoras dos Alunos	Changqing Lai; Wenjing Lv; Yuning Jiang	132 high school students from the Application School of Univali (CAU).
	Revista Pretexto	2015	Modelagem de intenção empreendedora de estudantes universitários usando equações estruturais	Sérgio Henrique de Oliveira Lima; Domenico Ceglia; Sílvia Maria Dias Pedro Rebouças; Aurora Amélia Castro Teixeira	Administration and Economics students from the Federal University of Ceará, Ceará.
	Revista Pensamento Contemporâneo em Administração	2016	Educação empreendedora: Premissas, objetivos e metodologias	Ricardo Schaefer; Italo Fernando Minello	Not Identified.
			Empreendedorismo educacional: reflexões para um ensino docente diferenciado	Jairo de Carvalho Guimarães e Marcos Antônio Martins Lima.	Faculty members who focus on the unifying factors of entrepreneurial initiative, especially in Administration courses.
		2018	Educação empreendedora, experiência e John Dewey	Gracyanne Freire de Araújo; Eduardo Davel	Undergraduate Administration students, Federal University of Sergipe.

continues

Chart 5 – Ranking of the 10 journals with the most publications and their respective studies, presented in order of quantity (continuation)

Qualis	JOURNAL TITLE	YEAR	ARTICLE TITLE	AUTHORS	PARTICIPANTS, COURSE OF THE RESEARCH, HEI, CITY AND STATE
B2	Revista Pensamento Contemporâneo em Administração	2018	Inovações nas técnicas pedagógicas para a formação de empreendedores	Marcos Hashimoto; Patrícia Viveiros de Castro; Aline Krakauer; Michelle Cardoso	Students from the hybrid school, Polifonia.
	Revista Desenvolvimento em Questão	2019	Aprendizagem Empreendedora Conhecendo o Passado e Vislumbrando o Futuro	Sérgio Vogt; Yara Lucia Mazziotti Bulgaco.	Not Identified.
			Universidade Empreendedora Proposição de Modelo Teórico	Sofia Maria de Araújo Ruiz; Cristina Dai Prá Martens	Not Identified.
	Revista Pensamento Contemporâneo em Administração	2020	Educação empreendedora: A prática docente estimulando a mente do estudante	Jairo de Carvalho Guimarães; Ildamara Ferreira dos Santos	The research subjects are students from the Federal University of Piauí (Administration course) and the Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology (Systems Analysis and Development course – ADS). Florianópolis, UFPI and IFPI.
	Open Journal of Social Science	2020	Experiential Approaches: Effective Pedagogy “for” Entrepreneurship in Entrepreneurship Education	Janeth Malywanga; Yongchuan Shi; Xiaoping Yang	Not Identified.
	Revista Desenvolvimento em Questão	2020	A Interação Entre as Universidades e o Empreendedorismo	Nairana Radtke Caneppele Bussler; José Eduardo Storopoli; Cristina Dai Prá Martens; Vânia Maria Jorge Nassif	Not Identified.

Source: Research data, 2023.

From Chart 5, it is possible to develop a systematization and analysis of the articles published during the study period. From 2000 to 2021 (22 years), research on Entrepreneurial Education involved students of Administration, Accounting Sciences, Economics, Civil Engineering, Electrical Engineering, Production Engineering, Health-related fields, and indigenous students. Similarly, it was noted that studies were conducted not only at the undergraduate level but also at the postgraduate level (*Stricto Sensu*), as well as studies in which course coordinators, directors of Higher Education Institutions, and faculty members teaching the subject of Entrepreneurship at the HEI shared their perspectives. Additionally, comparative studies were observed, involving HEIs and students from Brazilian and Portuguese universities, approaches with Secretarial students in Nigeria, micro-entrepreneurs from the South and Southeast regions of Brazil, Federal Higher Education Institutions (including Federal Institutes), research with junior entrepreneurs, and more.

This scenario indicates that the theme has evolved in the Brazilian territory, especially in academia, reflecting progress in discussions in its broadest forms across a variety of courses and transversal fields, which highlights the relevance of such studies, notably when considering the contribution of entrepreneurs in building new social and economic links in Brazil.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study aimed to analyze the characteristics of scientific production in the field of entrepreneurial education (EE) from 2000 to 2021 (22 years), represented by scientific articles published in QUALIS A1, A2, B1, and B2 journals (2013-2016 quadrennium), considering that at the research's start (August 2022), the new QUALIS (2017-2020 quadrennium) had not yet been published. During this period, a total of 71 articles published in nationally based journals were obtained, which, although discussing the role of EE in academia,

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related to various scopes and participants, always taking into account the theme's relevance in the historical context involved. The journals *Pensamento Contemporâneo em Administração* (UFF) and *Cadernos EBAPE* (FGV) accounted for 24% of the total collection with 17 publications.

The study shows, as seen in Chart 1, an increase in the number of publications on the topic, especially between 2016 and 2021, considering the six filters used in this study. This suggests that HEIs, where most of the research was developed, have, besides their natural social role of preparing students for the labor market, a fundamental role in constructing agendas that allow expanding debates on the theme to make it effective in all Course Pedagogical Projects (PPC).

Although the study was based on a 22-year time frame, the survey only considered articles published in nationally based journals. Therefore, to deepen the analysis of the subject, it is suggested for future research agendas to also consider articles published in international journals in order to broaden the scope of EE and its contribution to the formation of the social, political, economic, and cultural subject of contemporary times. It is suggested to highlight - regarding the didactic-pedagogical process adopted by faculty teaching the discipline(s) aimed at encouraging students to think entrepreneurially - the techniques used to attract students' attention and motivation, considering that academic training implies generating not only professional opportunities but, above all, the fixation of knowledge, self-efficacy, and know-how that will equip individuals with skills and technical handling to face the natural challenges of modernity. Under these conditions, entrepreneurship becomes a key piece in forming a new level of qualification, improvement, and capacity-building for people interested in and disposed toward the entrepreneurial segment.

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